

PROCESSING OF Zn-22%Al/SiC COMPOSITE BY SPRAY ATOMIZATION AND DEPOSITION

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ABSTRACT: The processing and superplastic deformation of SiC particulate reinforced Zn-22%Al alloy matrix composite was investigated in conjunction with systematic microstructural examination. The composite material was produced using variable co-deposition of multi-phase materials (VCM). The deposited material was then hot extruded and heat-treated to produce a microstructure suitable for superplastic deformation. The microstructures associated with the processing and deformation process were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The as-deposited composite exhibited a fine lamellar matrix microstructure with a distribution of the SiC particulates. High dislocation densities in the matrix region surrounding the particulates were noted in TEM observation. High temperature tensile test showed that the composite was superplastic and an elongation to failure of 370% was obtained at temperature $T = 463$ K and initial strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ s⁻¹. It was demonstrated that the processing route studied herein was efficient for the incorporation of SiC particulates into the Zn-22%Al.

KEYWORDS: SiC particulate, Zn-22%Al eutectoid, variable co-deposition of multi-phase materials (VCM), superplastic deformation, dislocation

INTRODUCTION

Metal-matrix composites (MMCs) have the potential of combining metallic properties of ductility, toughness and environmental resistance with reinforcement properties of high strength and high modulus. A variety of processing techniques have evolved in an effort to optimize the structure and properties of particulate reinforced MMCs [1-5]. The processes can be classified into three categories: (a) liquid phase processes such as liquid metal-ceramic particulate mixing, melt infiltration, melt oxidation; (b) solid phase processes such as powder metallurgy and high-energy-high-rate process; and (c) two-phase processes such as osprey deposition, rheocasting and variable co-deposition of multi-phase materials (VCM).

VCM has received considerable attention for the synthesis of aluminum-base alloys [6-7] and MMCs [8-11]. This novel technique involves processing in a regime of the phase diagram where the alloy is a mixture of solid and liquid phases. The matrix material is disintegrated into a fine dispersion of droplets using high velocity gas jets. One or more jets of strengthening phases are simultaneously injected into the atomized spray at a prescribed spatial location where the droplets contain a limited amount of volume fraction of liquid. Such an approach would inherently avoid the extreme thermal excursions with concomitant degradation in interfacial properties and extensive macrosegregation normally associated with conventional casting processes [12-13]. Furthermore, this approach also eliminates the need to handle fine reactive particulates, as is necessary with powder metallurgical processes [14-15].

Investigators have succeeded in incorporating SiC particulates into aluminum alloys using VCM. For example, a study on the wetting and interfacial behavior in a VCM processed Al-Li/SiCp MMC showed that there was sufficient interfacial activity at the Al-Li/SiC interface during deposition to establish a stable bond [16]. Severe interfacial reactions and the formation of oxide phases were noted when the spray deposited material was exposed to temperatures in excess of 873 K. Another example is the mechanical tests on the Al-Cu/SiC/Al₂O₃ MMC synthesized utilizing VCM technique [11]. The

results indicated that the presence of particulate reinforcement in the metal matrix does little to improve the strength, and degrades the ductility of the matrix material.

The objective of the present study was to study the synthesis of SiC particulate reinforced Zn-22%Al eutectoid alloy by VCM, and to perform structural evaluation of the synthesized materials using SEM and TEM. The Zn-22%Al eutectoid alloy was selected as the matrix material for three primary reasons. First, Zn-22%Al is a two-phase alloy with 57% volume fraction of the HCP Zn-rich phase and 43% volume fraction of the FCC Al-rich phase. This type of structure has heretofore not been studied for MMC synthesis via VCM. Second, the low melting temperature (695K) of the eutectoid composition may provide a potential advantage over previously studied Al alloy materials in terms of reducing interfacial reaction during processing. Third, Zn-22% Al is a ductile material that can undergo a high degree of plastic deformation, a condition that may shed light on the effects of reinforcement particulates on the ductility of the matrix material.

EXPERIMENT

The starting materials for high-pressure-gas-atomization were high purity Zn (99.999 purity) and Al (999.999 purity) elements supplied by Cominco Electronic Materials Inc. (Spokane, WA). The SiC particulates were obtained from the Superior Graphite Company. The size distribution of the SiC (α phase) was Gaussian and exhibited an average size of 3.5 μm . In addition, 90% of the distribution of SiC particulate sizes as less than 5 μm . In order to ensure moisture desorption from the surface, the particulates were vacuum degassed at 1073 K for 30 minutes prior to the experiments.

The Zn-22%Al/SiC MMC was produced according to the following procedure. The matrix material, bulk Zn and Al with eutectoid composite ratio, were superheated to 773 K (all the processing temperatures in the present study were determined based on Zn-Al phase diagram, see Figure 1) and delivered to an atomizer using a boron nitride delivery tube with a diameter of 3.0 mm. The eutectoid alloy was then disintegrated into a fine dispersion of droplets using high velocity gas jets (N_2) at a pre-selected pressure of 1.2 MPa. Simultaneously, a jet of strengthening phase, SiC particulate was injected into the atomized spray at a prescribed flight distance. The mixture of rapidly quenched, partially solidified droplets with inter-dispersed SiC particulates was deposited on a water-cooled rotating deposition surface, and eventually collected as a coherent perform (see the schematic diagram in Figure 2). The experiment was conducted in an environmental chamber to avoid extensive oxidation of the Zn-22%Al matrix. The chamber was evacuated to a negative pressure of 0.02 MPa, and backfilled with inert gas to a positive pressure of 0.014 MPa, prior to melting and atomization. The particulates were introduced into the atomized Zn-22%Al using a coaxial tube that entrained the SiC particulates as the gas flowed from the inlet to the out orifices at ambient temperature.

The deposited material was machined to a cylinder sample 5 cm in diameter and then extruded at 513 K with a ram speed of 3 cm/min and a extrusion ratio of 16:1 (the resultant rod is 1.25 cm in diameter). The extrusion step was used in this study to close the micrometer-sized porosity that is normally associated with spray atomized and deposited materials. The extruded rods were solution heat treated in argon atmosphere for 15 hr at 633K, ice water quenched to 273K, and finally annealed at 533 K

for 8 hrs. As a result of this annealing, an average linear grain size, , of 1.44 μm that corresponds to a spatial grain size of 2.5 μm was obtained. Tensile specimens with gauge length and

width of 3 mm were machined from the heat-treated material. The specimens were deformed to failure in

a silicon oil bath heated at 463 K and initial strain rates of 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} s^{-1} using an Instron machine.

Figure 1. Processing temperatures shown on the Zn-Al phase diagram

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of experimental arrangement for the VCM process

Figure 3. Microstructures of as-deposited Zn-22%Al/SiC composite a) and b) SEM showing the distribution of SiC particulates and the matrix structure, and c) TEM showing dislocations around SiC particulates

Figure 4. Microstructures of Zn-22%Al/SiC composite deformed at 463 K and $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, a) and b) SEM micrographs showing the SiC distribution and grain structure, c), d) and e) TEM micrographs showing dislocations activities during deformation

Table 1. Heats of formation of possible compounds formed during VCM [31]

Compound	Al_4C_3	AlN	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \alpha$	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \delta$	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rho$	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \kappa$	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \gamma$	$\text{Zn}(\text{CN})_2$	$\text{Zn}(\text{N}_3)_2$	Zn_3N_2	ZnO
$-\Delta H_{298}$ (kJ)	210	319.2	1680	1671	1642	1667	1659	-96.1	-218	22.4	349.6

SEM observations were performed on a Philips XL 30 microscope with a field emission gun. To obtain a clear topological image from Zn-22%Al samples, the acceleration voltages were set between 10- 12 KeV while the working distance was adjusted to about 10 mm. Samples for TEM were prepared by cutting thin slices, about 1 mm in thickness, from the bulk material. These slices were reduced to a thickness of about 30 μm by mechanical polishing. Thin foils were then placed in a jet-polishing machine to further reduce thickness to a few angstroms. To obtain a good thinning, the voltage and current were set to about 20V and 15 mA, respectively. The polishing solution of 20% perchloric acid and 80% ethanol was surrounded by a dry ice bath to keep the electrolyte temperature at 243 K. After jet-polished, the sample was immediately rinsed in ethanol and DI water. The thin foils prepared by this technique were examined in a PHILIPS CM-20 TEM equipped with a double-tilted stage at an accelerating voltage of 200 KeV. Dislocations analysis was conducted under a number of two-beam diffractions.

RESULTS

SEM micrographs of the as-deposited composite revealed a fine lamellar matrix microstructure with a distribution of the SiC particulate reinforcements (see Figure 3a and b). High dislocation densities in the matrix region surrounding the particulates were noted in TEM observation (see Fig. 3c). Image analysis was conducted on a number of representative SEM micrographs in order to characterize the size and distribution of SiC in the Zn-22%Al matrix. A histogram of the relative frequency of particle size *vs* particle size was constructed, yielding an average particle size of $d_p = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$. By counting N , the number of particles per unit area (using a number of representative micrographs), and by applying the expression [17]: $\lambda = 1.2/\sqrt{N}$, the average particle spacing, λ , was estimated to be about 14 μm . The volume fraction, V_f , of SiC particulates was estimated to be 7% using a chemical dissolution method. According to the formula discussed by Nardone and Prewo [18]: $\lambda = d_p/\sqrt{V_f}$, the average particle spacing was computed to be 13.2 μm . The values of λ obtained from the two methods are very close to each other. After thermomechanical treatment, the composite showed a similar distribution of SiC particulates but in a fine-equiaxed and two-phased matrix with grains size of 2.5 μm (see Fig. 4a and b). Extensive interactions, not only between dislocation and SiC particulates, but also between dislocations and nano-scale dispersions, were observed in the composite deformed under superplastic condition (see Figure 4c, d and e).

Regarding the results of tensile tests on the Zn-22%Al/7%SiC composite, the curve in Figure 5 shows the total elongations to failure $\Delta L/L_0$ (%), where ΔL is the increase in length and L_0 is the initial gauge length, as a function of initial strain rates. The maximum elongation of 370% was achieved at $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It can be seen that superplastic deformation occurs at intermediate strain rates and the ductility decreases at both low strain rate end and high strain rate end.

DISCUSSION

The experimental results show a fine lamellar matrix microstructure in the as-deposited material; this observation is not in agreement with previous findings [19-21] where a equiaxed grain morphology was noted. It has been proposed [22] that the formation of an equiaxed grain morphology during spray deposition is associated with three simultaneous processes: (1) dendrite arm fragmentation, (2) nucleation/grain multiplication, and (3) constrained growth. During deposition, there is extensive fragmentation of the dendrite arms formed during solidification, as a result of the repeated impact of the partially solidified droplets, first with the deposition surface, and subsequently, with each other. The presence of dendrite fragments, the development of strong convective currents in the liquid during impact, and the formation of a large number of solid nuclei have all been proposed as factors which contribute towards the development of an equiaxed grain morphology during spray atomization and deposition. However, in the present Zn-22%Al eutectoid system, with the melting temperature for Zn phase (692 K) being much lower than Al phase (933 K), both fragmentation and nucleation processes may be

significantly reduced due to the presence of high volume fraction liquid Zn phase, leading to the absence of equiaxed grain structure. Under the current experimental condition, the rate of temperature decreasing during solidification is not high enough to produce a large number of nuclei and to constrain grain growth during cooling. In addition, equiaxed two-phased microstructures were observed in some individual particles collected after the VCM process, suggesting: (1) it is possible to achieve an equiaxed grain morphology when cooling rate is high, and (2) relatively low cooling rate and high temperature were maintained at the deposition surface, which accounted for the development of the fine lamellar matrix microstructure.

The high dislocation density observed in the Zn-22%Al matrix adjacent to the SiC particulates is in agreement with previous findings [20, 23]. This high dislocation density can be attributed to the large difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of Al and SiC (10:1) which causes thermal mismatch strains between reinforcement and matrix during solid state cooling. These strains are relaxed by the formation of a dislocation network.

The presence of a finite amount of non-interconnected porosity has been reported to be associated with spray-atomized and deposited microstructures [19-21]. It was suggested [16] that the porosity develops from interstices formed as droplets impact on one another. The overall amount of porosity depends on the thermodynamic properties of the material and the processing parameters. Under conditions typical for aluminum alloys, the amount of porosity present in spray-atomized and deposited materials has been reported to be in the 1-10% range [21, 24]. In VCM process, with the presence of ceramic particulates, the volume fraction of porosity was shown to be higher when compared to that of the unreinforced matrix material processed under identical conditions [11]. This is attributed in part to enhanced heat transfer and the concurrent increase in solid fraction of the droplets prior to deposition. However, SEM observation revealed that the Zn-22%Al/7%SiC material processed by VCM was almost porosity-free. The reduced amount of porosity can be accounted for by the presence of high volume fraction of liquid phase (Zn-phase) at the deposition surface. The interstices formed in between impacting droplets can be efficiently fulfilled by the liquid phase during deposition.

The volume fraction of ceramic particulates present in VCM materials has been correlated with processing parameters such as injection angle, injection pressure and ceramic/metal mass flow ration, and physical properties such as surface tension of the atomized droplets [16, 21]. Two possible mechanisms responsible for the incorporation of the ceramic particulates into the metal matrix are: (1) the ceramic particulates penetrate the atomized droplets during co-injection and remain entrapped in the matrix during subsequent impact with the deposition surface, and (2) SiC particulates remain on the surface of the atomized droplets and are entrapped by the matrix after impact with the deposition surface. If entrapment fails to take place either during co-injection, or subsequently, during deposition, the microstructure of the VCM material will be characterized by a high concentration of ceramic particulates at the prior droplet boundaries. Such a situation was not noted for the Zn-22%Al/7%SiC system, indicating entrapment of the SiC particulates by a large proportion of the droplet population. It is worth noting that SiC particulates are generally homogeneously distributed although there is a tendency to agglomerate into clusters in some localized regions, frequently inside the lamellar matrix microstructure.

TEM studies on the specimens deformed under superplastic condition revealed extensive interactions between dislocations and dispersion particles (Figures 4). This observation is consistent with the previous suggestion that oxide particles can be introduced into the material as a result of processing the composite by powder metallurgy [25-29]. It was reported that a thin oxide layer formed at the surface of Al-6.5Zn-2.5Mg-1.5Cu alloy powders atomized in helium [30]. In the present Zn-22%Al alloy, the formation of the Al₂O₃ and AlN phases is favored over Zn₂N₃ and ZnO from the viewpoint of energies involved (the heats of formation of possible compounds formed during cryomilling are listed in Table 1 [31]). The Al₂O₃/AlN layer can be broken up to small pieces during deposition and hot extrusion, forming

nano-scale dispersions. These incoherent dispersion particulates can serve as effective barriers to dislocation motion and thus influences the deformation behavior of the material. For example, the interaction between dislocation and dispersion particulates was suggested to be critical in determining the high-temperature creep of PM Al and their discontinuous composites [25-30].

Figure 5. Elongation to failure as a function of initial strain rate of the thermomechanically treated Zn-22%Al/7 vol.%SiC composite particulates

CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary results presented in this study have indicated that VCM is an efficient method for preparing Zn-22%Al/ SiC composite. The resultant composite showed a homogeneous distribution of SiC particulate in a fine two-phased lamellar matrix. The high volume fraction of liquid-phase (Zn) in the atomized droplet and at the deposition surface was suggested to be responsible for (1) the lamellar, rather than equiaxed, matrix microstructure, (2) the absence of significant micro-porosity, and (3) the enhanced entrapment of SiC particulates into the matrix. The nano-scale dispersion particulates introduced by VCM process can serve as effective barriers to dislocation motion and thus influences the mechanical behavior of the material.

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